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‘Sharing the space’ in the agricultural knowledge and innovation system: multi-actor innovation partnerships with farmers and foresters in Europe

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Networks and partnerships are commonly-used tools to foster knowledge sharing between actors and organisations in the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS), but in Europe the policy emphasis on including users, such as farmers and foresters, is relatively recent. This paper assesses user involvement in a diverse set of European Union (EU)-funded and non-EU (formal and informal) multi-actor partnerships.

Design/methodology/approach: A review of 200 projects and other partnerships including farmers and foresters, drawn from an integrated database of several thousand such examples, assessed the types of innovation challenges tackled, solutions proposed, innovation supported, parameters of actor participation and the expectations of success in each example.

Findings: All the reviewed policy instruments, not just those funded in the frame of the EIP-AGRI, can be used to involve users in co-innovation in agriculture, forestry and related value chains.

Practical implications: The EIP-AGRI is just one part of a complex matrix of multi-actor co-innovation activities involving farmers and foresters in Europe. Interlinking of innovation programmes and more effective targeting of these programmes at groups of actors, especially users, who are currently not sufficiently engaged are worthy aspirations.

Theoretical implications: Any analysis of co-innovation involving users must recognise the existence of a multiplicity (projects, non-project activities, formal and informal) of multi-actor approaches.

Originality/value: This research used a common methodology to review several forms of multi-actor partnerships involving users and other actors. Our data suggest that many of these are effective methods of supporting co-innovation and are, therefore, ‘sharing the space’ within the AKIS.

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Introduction

The Horizon 2020 (H2020) funded multi-actor project LIAISON (Better Rural Innovation: Linking Actors, Instruments and Policies through Networks) is expected to make a significant and meaningful contribution to optimising interactive innovation project approaches and the delivery of European Union (EU) policies to speed up innovation in agriculture, forestry and related sectors. Using a common methodology, we reviewed the design and implementation of 200 multi-actor partnerships involving farmers and foresters from across Europe. These included activities supported by recognised innovation policy instruments and others that were not. We assessed the types of innovation challenges tackled, solutions proposed, innovation supported, parameters of actor participation and the expectations of success. From our findings, we developed recommendations for improving the targeting and interlinking of policy instruments, and on the need for academics and policy-makers to pay more attention to the important role of value chain co-innovation in the AKIS.

Innovation appears now, not primarily as a single event, but rather as a process (Lundvall 2016). Well-documented developments in innovation systems thinking (Rivera et al. 2006; Klerkx, van Mierlo, and Leeuwis 2012) have led to the recognition that, alongside the traditional process of 'knowledge transfer' (with research as the source of knowledge, extension and education as knowledge and information channels, and farmers as passive recipients of knowledge), innovation can be 'co-produced' through interactions between farmers, researchers, intermediate actors (input providers, experts, distributors, etc.) and consumers. In this process of 'co-innovation', actors jointly identify problems and co-create solutions through a collective learning process involving knowledge sharing (Nederlof, Wongtschowski, and Van Der Lee 2011; Dogliotti et al. 2014). The potential contribution of co-innovation to agricultural development is now accepted in global (FAO 2014) and EU policy discourses.

Innovation does not occur in isolation and the innovators are not the sole agents of change. Several additional factors play a key role, such as policy, legislation, infrastructure, funding and market developments (Klerkx, van Mierlo, and Leeuwis 2012). In the EU, policy instruments to support farmer and forester participation in multi-actor innovation partnerships have their foundations in the development, via several Framework Programme research projects, of the 'Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System' (AKIS) model (Knickel et al. 2009; Dockès, Tisenkopfs, and Bock 2011; Knierim, Boenning, et al. 2015). Defined as 'a concept that seeks to encompass and influence the complexity of knowledge and innovation processes in the rural sphere' (Dockès, Tisenkopfs, and Bock 2011, 7), the AKIS embraces the actors, their organisation(s) and the knowledge flows between them. The concept was operationalised into policy mainly by the Standing Committee of Agricultural Research (SCAR) Strategic Working Group (SWG) on AKIS (EU SCAR 2012 and subsequent publications) in consultation with the European Commission's (EC) Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development (DG AGRI).

Consequently, the European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI) was introduced as a tool to speed up innovation in agriculture, forestry and rural development and to create synergies between different policy programmes both at the EU and Member State level (DG AGRI 2018). Central to the

EIP-AGRI approach is the ‘interactive innovation model’, defined as: ‘the collaboration between various actors to make best use of complementary types of knowledge (scientific, practical, organisational etc.) in view of co-creation and diffusion of solutions/opportunities ready to implement in practice’ (EIP-AGRI SP 2017, 3). EIP-AGRI projects, whether those funded by Horizon 2020 or ‘Operational Groups’ (OG), which are funded from Rural Development Programmes (RDP) and which focus on real problems or opportunities that farmers, foresters or others are facing, are required to apply the ‘multi-actor approach’ from beginning to end (EIP-AGRI SP 2017).

While the EIP-AGRI is unique among EU policy instruments in stressing the need to include farmers and foresters (i.e. ‘practitioners’ or ‘users’¹) in co-innovation partnerships, it has two conceptual shortcomings. Firstly, activities are implemented solely in the form of ‘projects’, i.e. single, non-divisible interventions with fixed time schedules and dedicated budgets, as defined by O’Neill et al. (2012). In practice, however, co-innovation can be delivered according to several different models which engage actors in dynamic multi-stakeholder innovation systems or in iterative learning for change processes (Ingram et al. 2020). These other ‘actor configurations’ include networks, platforms, clusters, alliances and partnerships (Knierim, Koutsouris, et al. 2015). Unlike projects, they might not be fixed term or be implemented by a ‘consortium’ (a defined group of partners working on a formal basis). We use the term ‘partnership’ when referring collectively to projects and non-project activities.

Secondly, there is an implicit emphasis in the EIP-AGRI on translating research knowledge into practical applications. This equates in the EU SCAR (2012) visual depiction of the AKIS (see 9) to knowledge sharing between farmers and the (mainly public sector) education and research institutes, and advisory services, a reflection of the persistent ‘linear’ approach to innovation described above. Yet knowledge sharing between the (mainly private sector) actors in the value chain, including input suppliers and food processors, is where much of the on-farm technology or food retail innovation takes place (Swinnen and Kuijpers 2019). Knowledge sharing between farmers (Kilpatrick and Johns 2007; Oreszczyn, Lane, and Carr 2010) and foresters (Hamunen et al. 2015) themselves can also foster co-innovation. Indeed, Koutsouris et al. (2017) observed that farmers tend to be most influenced by proof of successful farming methods by their peers, so-called peer-to-peer learning.

Furthermore, despite the overall success of the EIP-AGRI in fostering farmer-led co-innovation (Fotheringham et al. 2016), its potential impact may be limited in at least two respects. The first concerns its ability to engage with harder-to-reach groups of users, i.e. those sections of the community that are difficult to involve in public participation (Brackertz 2007). Barriers to user co-design of and participation in farming programmes include lack of time (farmers are ‘too busy’), policy and bureaucracy, the digital divide, geographical factors (at a local/regional level such as remote areas with poor communications), lack of social capital, lack of trust, low income, age, farm type and learning disabilities (Hurley et al. 2020).

Openness to innovation is frequently analysed according to the ‘diffusion of innovation’ theory (Rogers 1962) with adopters variously categorised from ‘innovators’ through to ‘laggards’. The validity of this theory has long been robustly challenged (Albrecht 1963; Hoffman 2005). Of particular concern is the implicit suggestion that ‘laggards’ are somehow ‘at fault’ and can potentially be motivated to innovate or adopt

an innovation. In fact, farmers may be aware of an innovation but conclude that it is not in their best interests to adopt it (Hoffman 2005).

There is indeed increasing empirical evidence that many farmers decide to innovate not only on the basis of economic and personal considerations, but also in the context of the social interactions they maintain among themselves and with the broad range of agents who promote change, such as buyers, input providers, local authorities, farmers' groups and others (Knierim, Koutsouris, et al. 2015; Fieldsend et al. 2019). Embeddedness in social networks is a crucial factor in an equation that explains farmers' decisions to innovate (Chávez and Hartwich 2011). In other words, this embeddedness fosters openness to innovation by mitigating the barriers listed above. Certain groups of users, such as small and family farms (including semi-subsistence farms, those in remote areas and those managed by women), tend to be less well embedded into social networks (FAO 2014) and are potentially harder to reach.

When funding and other resources are limited, there is a tendency for programmes to 'pick the low-hanging fruit' and it is the farmers who are already well connected to EU networks that are likely to benefit most from the EIP-AGRI, quite possibly on multiple occasions, while the mass of users will not be engaged at all. Fotheringham et al. (2016) observed that only several thousand farms, i.e. just a small proportion of the 20 million farming businesses across the EU, will be directly involved in the EIP-AGRI through participation in OGs or related initiatives.

The second concern is the suitability of the EIP-AGRI for implementation in all regions of the EU. In the current (2014–2020) programming period, by far the largest numbers of OGs are planned for the Western EU Member States. Of the 3205 OGs planned in April 2016, Spain accounted for 849, Italy for 625, Greece for 435, France for 305 and Germany for 203 (EIP-AGRI SP 2016). Between them, 9 of the 11 post-socialist Member States were planning just 298 OGs, with Poland envisaging 90 and Hungary 70, while Estonia and Latvia were not expecting to fund any such groups.

The OG model is, therefore, being adopted only with extreme caution in the transition economies of Eastern Europe and this geographical imbalance may persist. Over 10 years ago, Gorton, Hubbard, and Hubbard (2009) questioned the wisdom of transferring EU agricultural and rural policy developed in countries with a long tradition of family farming to post-socialist EU Member States with rural areas that are substantially different in terms of their underlying historical and socio-economic conditions. The process assumed that former collectivised structures would naturally adjust to the Western European norm (Swain 2013). In fact, these structural differences can lead to different interests and priorities regarding research and innovation funding (Pokrivčák, Ciaian, and Drabik 2019). Augustyn and Nemes (2014) agreed that 'Europeanisation' in rural development has been mostly a one-way process of transferring the EU-15 policy models into the post-socialist realm, with incomplete success, while Nemes, High, and Augustyn (2014) reported that LEADER as a rural development model has been difficult to operate in the post-socialist countries. Similar challenges may continue to be encountered with the implementation of the EIP-AGRI.

Despite its merits, therefore, the EIP-AGRI approach has several potential limitations. But, beyond the EIP-AGRI, other forms of multi-actor innovation partnerships, including farmers and foresters, occur widely across Europe. Indeed, the AKIS is a 'space' in which numerous knowledge sharing and co-innovation activities are occurring

through a matrix of networks and partnerships. In this paper, we describe how the EIP-AGRI and a range of other EU-supported and non-EU (formal and informal) co-innovation activities are ‘sharing the space’ in the AKIS. Following the presentation of our research results, we discuss the emerging research, practical and policy implications.

Methodology

Reflecting the focus of our research on multi-actor partnerships involving users, we selected 200 projects and non-project activities for review that complied with 5 criteria. These included (a) involving a *multi-actor partnership* composed of two or more entities; (b) having a clear *intention to innovate* in (c) a *relevant topic*; and (d) featuring a substantial level of *engagement with practitioners*. In other words, it was necessary for farmers, foresters and/or their organisations to be involved in the co-innovation process, usually as participants in the core partnership, although ‘substantial engagement’ could occasionally be achieved in other ways in some other ‘actor configurations’ (such as networks). Finally, *the quality of the published description* had to allow an assessment of whether the activity was likely to be ‘insightful’ in terms of yielding useful information.

The reviewed examples were shortlisted from two main sources (Figure 1) during the first quarter of 2019. Firstly, using keyword searches, 1357 candidate projects were identified from a compiled database of several thousand such examples drawn from EU databases (Table 1). The main source (yielding 523 candidates) was the EIP-AGRI project database. Every consulted database was uniquely structured and, of necessity, different keywords were used to shortlist projects from each (Fieldsend, Cronin, and Rønningen 2019). National project databases were compiled locally by each LIAISON partner under close supervision.

Recognising that these databases would not adequately sample the range of multi-actor partnership approaches that exist, a second source was an EU-wide Rural Innovation Contest (EURIC) held by the LIAISON project aimed at identifying less formal examples of co-innovation. The call for entries was widely publicised by the consortium partners through many channels, including the farming, rural, policy and local media, within EU Member States and several neighbouring countries, and attracted 175 eligible entries from 20 countries. They were termed ‘under-the-radar’ activities as many of them were not included in published databases and/or not known to EU and/or national policy-makers.

To ensure a diversity of multi-actor co-innovation activities for review, a purposive stratified sampling frame was applied. The EIP-AGRI was represented by 87 projects (Figure 2), including 34 H2020 Research and Innovation Actions (RIA), 16 Thematic Networks (TN) and 37 OGs from 14 EU Member States. The other 74 projects included EU Interreg and LIFE projects, projects funded by RDPs in 10 EU Member States, projects nationally funded in 9 countries (including Norway and Switzerland), and some funded by other sources including the private sector. Of the 39 non-project activities, 25 were externally funded and 14 were not. Around three-quarters of the sample were agriculture related, 5 per cent concerned forestry and just over 20 per cent dealt with food chain topics.

The reviews were conducted by the LIAISON consortium partners in the period May–July 2019 and consisted of three phases. Firstly, desk research from published information was undertaken by the project partners and the results subsequently checked

Figure 1. Selection pathway of the 200 co-innovation projects and non-project activities.

with the interviewees. Secondly, a ‘one telephone call’ semi-structured interview was held with a key informant, involving questions related to the partnership, cooperation within it, its performance and outcomes, and a short self-evaluation. Of the interviewees, 128 described themselves as being ‘coordinator’, ‘project leader’ or in a comparable role, a further 21 occupied evidently senior positions such as ‘managing director’ and the remaining 51 were ‘project partners’ or similar. Among them, 84 were female, 115 were male and 3 were not defined. Thirdly, a post-interview reflection by the LIAISON partner was intended to obtain some first insights into the factors they thought were keys to the success of the project or causes of failure or were barriers to

Table 1. European Union databases from which the projects for review were sourced.

Database name	Database URL	No. of projects	
		Total	Shortlisted
EIP-AGRI	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects?title=&field_proj_funding_source_list=0&search_api_views_fulltext=&=Search	641	523
H2020 Thematic Networks	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/about/thematic-networks-%E2%80%93-closing-research-and	29	29
H2020 'multi-actor' projects	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/about/multi-actor-projects-scientists-and-farmers	77	77
Knottter et al. (2019)	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/sites/agri-eip/files/eip-agri_operational_groups_assessment_2018_data_projects_involved.xlsx	611	260 ^a
ENRD 'Projects and practice'	https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/projects-practice_en	348	69
Interreg Europe	https://www.interregeurope.eu/discover-projects/	1504	52
KEEP (Interreg projects)	https://www.keep.eu/search	2187	136
LIFE programme	http://ec.europa.eu/environment/life/project/Projects/index.cfm	4932	211

^aAdditional OGs not included in the EIP-AGRI database.

Figure 2. Percentage of each type of project and non-project activity by 'domain'.

Note: in all figures and tables, the numbers of each partnership type are shown in parentheses.

efficient implementation. This methodology ensured that a considerable amount of data was gathered very efficiently from 200 co-innovation partnerships. A standard data gathering template was used for all reviews, and the results were collated into a single database for analysis.

Methods described in two papers aided the interpretation of our data. Firstly, Knottter et al. (2019) reviewed the setting-up and implementation of the 611 OGs that were approved and running under the EIP-AGRI until April 2018, together with their results and how these were disseminated. Their analysis included a clustering exercise that firstly required the development of sets of categories that were sufficiently representative for each OG to be associated with them. These categories covered the types of challenges tackled by the project (e.g. resource management, food safety and climate change),

the types of solutions proposed (e.g. new technologies and value chain innovations) and the types of participating actors. The evident success of this approach when applied to multi-actor projects (OGs) prompted us to adopt it for our own analysis.

Secondly, Lamprinopolou et al. (2014) defined four broad groups of actors in the AKIS and these can be equated to the categorisation of Knotter et al. (2019) as follows: *research*: researcher; *direct demand/enterprise*: business, individual farmer or forester, processing or marketing SME and representative/supporting organisation; *indirect demand*: public body and NGO; *intermediary*: advisor, education, and processing or marketing producer organisation. We found this framework helpful for clarifying the extent of participation of different groups of actors in our reviewed partnerships.

Since the research was to be conducted by 17 LIAISON partners from 15 countries, the methodology was designed to maximise consistency and replicability of the results. Nonetheless, two limitations should be noted. Firstly, despite the good results from the EURIC, numerous multi-actor partnerships that are not included in databases will have escaped our notice. Secondly, the cultural and organisational backgrounds of the survey participants could potentially influence the way certain concepts have been translated and interpreted. For this reason, the potential success of the co-innovation process, the issue that was arguably the most sensitive to cultural interpretation, was assessed both by the interviewees (according to four criteria) and the interviewers.

Findings

Multi-actor partnerships: challenges, solutions and types of innovation covered

The reviewed partnerships are diverse in terms of challenges addressed, solutions proposed and types of innovation supported. This finding applies both to the 87 EIP-AGRI projects and 113 non-EIP-AGRI projects and non-project activities.

The profiles of challenges tackled by each type of partnership are presented in Table 2. The H2020 projects are relatively evenly distributed across the challenges. The reviewed OGs also have a broad focus, although almost 50 per cent of them cover resource management (R) and almost 50 per cent deal with socio-economic sustainability (S) (several OGs may cover both topics, of course).

Table 2. Percentage of each type of project and non-project activity tackling a specific challenge.

Funding source and type	A	B	C	D	F	O	P	R	S
Horizon 2020 RIA and IA (34)	17.6	23.5	32.4	20.6	41.2	17.6	11.8	38.2	26.5
H2020 Them. Networks (16)	37.5	37.5	6.3	6.3	37.5	50.0	6.3	31.3	31.3
Interreg A, B and C projects (20)	5.0	15.0	25.0	0.0	40.0	40.0	0.0	30.0	60.0
LIFE+ and LIFE projects (8)	37.5	50.0	62.5	12.5	25.0	12.5	25.0	12.5	12.5
Operational Groups (37)	29.7	27.0	16.2	8.1	35.1	13.5	8.1	45.9	48.6
Other ESIF, ERASMUS (20)	5.0	0.0	25.0	15.0	25.0	50.0	0.0	30.0	50.0
National/regional public (11)	27.3	9.1	18.2	0.0	18.2	27.3	27.3	36.4	54.5
Projects: other sources (15)	13.3	20.0	6.7	13.3	40.0	26.7	6.7	40.0	46.7
Non-projects with funding (25)	12.0	28.0	20.0	8.0	28.0	12.0	4.0	44.0	60.0
Non-projects not funded (14)	28.6	21.4	7.1	0.0	57.1	28.6	7.1	21.4	21.4
All projects/non-projects (200)	19.5	23.0	21.0	10.0	36.5	25.5	8.0	36.5	44.0

Notes: Totals for each type of projects exceed 100 per cent because up to three challenges per project could be specified. Key: A: animal health/welfare; B: biodiversity/nature/landscape management; C: climate change; D: plant disease and pest treatment; F: food safety/product quality; O: other; P: pollution; R: resource management; S: socio-economic sustainability.

Many of the reviewed Interreg projects (and also other ESIF-funded and ERASMUS+ projects) address socio-economic sustainability and, to a lesser extent, food safety/product quality (F), while topics of more relevance to practical farming such as animal health/welfare (A), plant disease and pest treatment (D) and pollution (P) are only weakly represented. The relatively small number of LIFE and LIFE+ projects in the sample are focused towards environmental/climate topics (B and C).

Socio-economic sustainability (S) is also the challenge most frequently addressed by the reviewed national/regional level projects, and by non-project activities with funding, and around 40 per cent of these projects tackle resource management issues (R). By contrast, the high incidence (57.1 per cent) of food safety/product quality among the non-project activities without funding hints that the participants may be expecting product development to yield an early return on investment.

Production changes – new production practice/methods (PP) is the dominant type of solution proposed by the reviewed partnerships, accounting for 37.7 per cent of the total sample and exceeding 30 per cent among almost all types of projects and non-project activities except for Interreg and other ESIF-funded and ERASMUS+ projects (Figure 3). This type of solution is especially favoured by OGs (56.8 per cent), LIFE+ and LIFE projects (50.0 per cent) and H2020 RIAs (47.1 per cent). New technology solutions (ND and NP) and value chain innovations (VB, VC, VL, VP and VS) are the focus of around 19 and 22 per cent, respectively, of all reviewed projects and non-project activities.

As regards the type of innovation supported, more than 50 per cent of reviewed H2020 RIAs and OGs address process innovation (P) and this type is also dominant among H2020 TNs and projects funded from other sources (Figure 4). Around 20 per cent of

Figure 3. Percentage of each type of project and non-project activity proposing a specific type of solution. Key: N: new technology solutions – digital-based solutions (D), physical infrastructure (P); O: other; P: production changes – new business models/diversification (B), new production practice/methods (P); V: value chain innovations – branding, marketing, promoting and communication (B), certification, standardisation, quality assurance framework (C), logistics and distributions (L), new product development/introduction (P), value/supply chain optimisation (S).

Figure 4. Percentage of each type of project and non-project activity supporting a specific type of innovation. Key: M: marketing; N: organisational; O: other; P: process; S: social; T: product.

reviewed EIP-AGRI projects support product innovation (T). By contrast, the reviewed EIP-AGRI projects rarely address marketing (M) or social (S) innovation, while among them organisational innovation (N) is only weakly represented.

Organisational and social innovation feature among the reviewed Interreg projects and social innovation dominates among the LIFE+ and LIFE projects. Product innovation is supported by over 35 per cent of non-project activities, with process and social innovation also featuring strongly among these. Product innovation is especially common among the non-project activities without funding, which again may reflect expectations of an early financial return on investment.

Our 200 reviewed examples address many different challenges, propose a variety of solutions and support several different types of innovation, but this observation also applies to EIP-AGRI projects and non-EIP-AGRI partnerships separately. Thus, while clear differences in focus between programmes do occur, our data suggest that, in many situations, alternative options to the EIP-AGRI are available to prospective co-innovation partnerships.

Actor participation in multi-actor partnerships

Farmers, foresters and their representative organisations can be involved in all types of reviewed multi-actor partnerships, but there is notable variation in the nature of their participation.

The number of partners was normally counted in terms of the number of organisations (not individuals). For international EU-funded projects, this figure was easily defined, but in some other instances, it was difficult to distinguish the core partnership from the wider periphery of stakeholders (Figure 5). H2020 RIAs had on average the largest consortia with almost 80 per cent of the reviewed projects having 21 partners or more. This reflects their wide geographical coverage and big budgets. Few H2020

Figure 5. Number of partners in the partnership by percentage of type of project and non-project activity. Key: NQ: the number of partners could not be quantified.

TN consortia exceeded 20 partners, while more than half of all other projects and non-project activities had 10 partners or fewer.

Researchers (R) are very strongly represented in all types of projects funded in the frame of EIP-AGRI while individual farmers or foresters are participants in over 80 per cent of OGs (Table 3). Either they or their representatives are involved in all but one OG, are very strongly represented in H2020 TNs and only slightly less so in H2020 RIAs.² Extensive user participation is also evident in other types of projects and in the reviewed non-project activities with external funding. Lower rates of involvement are recorded for Interreg and LIFE+/LIFE projects. While the benefits of including farmers, foresters and/or their representative organisations in projects funded by these programmes depend on the topic to be addressed, our results show that they *can* be involved.

Advisors (A) participate in around two-thirds of OGs and are included in more than 50 per cent of H2020 project consortia. Business (B) (e.g. IT providers) is also quite strongly represented in the reviewed projects, notably H2020 RIAs, LIFE+ and LIFE projects, and non-project activities. Public bodies (G) take part in 75 per cent of reviewed Interreg projects and are represented in around two-thirds of projects funded from national and/or regional public sources. The overall picture is one of the substantial levels of participation by diverse actors in the reviewed partnerships.

The same system of categorisation of actors was applied to the coordinators of innovation partnerships. Unsurprisingly, almost all reviewed H2020 RIAs are coordinated by researchers (R) or educational institutions (E) (Figure 6). These two groups are however somewhat less dominant as regards coordinating H2020 TNs. Approximately 25 per cent of the reviewed OGs are coordinated by researchers, with advisors (A), NGOs (N), processing or marketing producer organisations (O) and representative/supporting organisations (S) coordinating 10 per cent or more of this type of project.

Public bodies (G) coordinate 40 per cent of reviewed Interreg projects and researchers also feature strongly as coordinators of national and/or regional publicly funded projects.

Table 3. Percentage of each type of project and non-project activity including a specific type of actor in the consortium (or equivalent).

Funding source and type	A	B	E	F	G	M	N	O	R	S	F/S
Horizon 2020 RIA and IA (34)	58.8	67.6	67.6	32.4	50.0	29.4	38.2	38.2	100	64.7	79.4
H2020 Them. Networks (16)	56.3	56.3	62.5	25.0	37.5	31.3	50.0	37.5	87.5	68.8	87.5
Interreg A, B and C projects (20)	50.0	40.0	45.0	30.0	75.0	20.0	45.0	30.0	75.0	60.0	70.0
LIFE+ and LIFE projects (8)	37.5	62.5	62.5	37.5	25.0	0.0	50.0	12.5	87.5	50.0	62.5
Operational Groups (37)	67.6	45.9	27.0	81.1	32.4	13.5	29.7	24.3	83.8	51.4	97.3
Other ESIF, ERASMUS (20)	45.0	55.0	45.0	55.0	40.0	40.0	40.0	35.0	65.0	60.0	90.0
National/regional public (11)	54.5	45.5	27.3	63.6	63.6	18.2	54.5	0.0	72.7	81.8	90.9
Projects: other sources (15)	40.0	33.3	33.3	66.7	40.0	13.3	20.0	26.7	53.3	26.7	73.3
Non-projects with funding (25)	48.0	60.0	52.0	84.0	48.0	28.0	36.0	32.0	76.0	56.0	92.0
Non-projects not funded (14)	28.6	57.1	14.3	57.1	42.9	21.4	35.7	35.7	42.9	21.4	64.3
All projects/non-projects (200)	53.0	55.0	45.5	58.0	46.0	24.0	40.0	30.5	79.5	57.5	85.5

Key: A: advisor; B: business; E: education; F: individual farmer or forester; G: public body; M: processing or marketing SME; N: NGO; O: processing or marketing producer organisation; R: researcher; S: representative/supporting organisation.

Figure 6. Percentage of each type of project and non-project activity by coordinator. Key: see Table 3; also X: other.

For other types of projects (and for non-project activities), no one type of actor is dominant as a coordinator, although business coordinates more than 20 per cent of the reviewed non-project activities. Furthermore, around 20 per cent of non-EIP-AGRI partnerships are coordinated by farmers' organisations and almost 30 per cent of non-funded non-project activities are led by individual farmers.

All types of AKIS actors participate in all forms of partnerships, and high levels of individual farmer and/or farmers' organisation representation can occur in both EIP-AGRI projects and non-EIP-AGRI partnerships. The involvement of some groups of actors (G, N) as formal partners is especially low in our sampled H2020 projects and OGs, and non-EIP-AGRI options may be better suited to fostering co-innovation between these actors and farmers and foresters. Clearly, therefore, the latter are viable alternatives for multi-actor innovation partnerships involving users.

Co-innovation in multi-actor partnerships

The potential success of the co-innovation process was judged to be medium or high in almost all the 200 reviewed multi-actor partnerships.

Since ‘success’ is very difficult to quantify directly, interviewees were asked to evaluate the performance of their co-innovation activity according to four rather more tangible criteria on a 1–10 Likert scale where 1 was ‘very low’ and 10 was ‘very high’. The mean score among the 200 projects was 8.2 for *innovation*, 7.7 for *research and acquisition of new knowledge*, 7.8 for *communication and outreach*, and 8.1 for *success of implementation* (i.e. what has been achieved (to date) compared to what was initially intended) (Table 4). Also, LIAISON interviewers assessed the level of co-innovation in the reviewed projects. Only 10 per cent of the projects and 3 per cent of the non-project activities were judged to involve only a low level of co-innovation.

A more in-depth and complex evaluation strategy would be necessary to demonstrate adequately the degree of co-innovation in the reviewed multi-actor partnerships, but the shared assessment of the participants and LIAISON interviewers was that co-innovation in agriculture, forestry and related value chains was occurring in activities both within and outside the EIP-AGRI.

Discussion

Almost all the reviewed multi-actor partnerships claimed medium to high levels of co-innovation. On average, our interviewees scored the potential success of their co-innovation activity highly, while the interviewers assessed the level of co-innovation as being ‘medium’ or ‘high’ in over 90 per cent of instances (Table 4). Clearly, therefore, in addition to the EIP-AGRI, multi-actor co-innovation in agriculture, forestry and related value chains involving users can be supported by many other policy instruments in Europe, both EU and non-EU, while several non-project activities, including formal and informal partnerships, and even activities with no external funding, have the same potential.

Our data also suggest, however, that although the reviewed partnerships can between them address a wide range of challenges, solutions and innovations, certain types of partnerships can more strongly promote the inclusion of specific groups of AKIS actors (e.g.

Table 4. Potential success of the co-innovation process by funding source as assessed by (a) interviewees according to four criteria and (b) interviewers (% of projects).

Funding source and type	Interviewees' criteria				Interviewers' assessments (%)		
	I	K	C	F	High	Medium	Low
Horizon 2020 RIA and IA (34)	8.5	8.7	8.5	8.4	56.3	43.7	0
H2020 Them. Networks (16)	8.3	7.1	8.5	8.8	53.3	40.0	6.7
Interreg A, B and C projects (20)	7.4	7.1	7.3	8.0	47.4	36.8	15.8
LIFE+ and LIFE projects (8)	7.9	7.0	8.4	7.4	87.5	0.0	12.5
Operational Groups (37)	8.0	7.7	7.8	8.0	52.6	42.1	5.3
Other ESIF, ERASMUS (20)	8.0	7.2	8.1	7.8	27.8	55.6	16.6
National/regional public (11)	8.5	8.3	7.3	7.5	36.4	54.5	9.1
Projects: other sources (15)	8.5	8.5	7.3	9.1	46.7	33.3	20.0
Non-projects with funding (25)	8.4	8.0	7.2	7.4	54.2	41.7	4.2
Non-projects not funded (14)	8.7	6.9	6.8	8.8	71.4	21.4	7.1
All projects/non-projects (200)	8.2	7.7	7.8	8.1	51.8	39.9	8.3

Key: I: innovation; K: acquisition of new knowledge; C: communication/outreach; F: fulfilment of initial expectations.

Interreg for public bodies) or are more suited to particular topics (e.g. LIFE(+) for environment-related issues). This illustrates the need to recognise and maintain the diversity of co-innovation opportunities for AKIS actors so as to ensure that a wide range of challenges is tackled by different types of solutions. This is necessary in view of the increasing complexity of societal challenges for which there are no ‘one size fits all’ innovations (Ingram et al. 2020).

Any analysis of the co-innovation landscape in Europe by the EC, policy-makers and policy implementers, as well as prospective innovation actors (cf. Kujala, Virkkala, and Lähdesmäki 2020) must, therefore, recognise that a multiplicity of approaches ‘share the space’ in the AKIS. For the latter group, this means being aware of the numerous different options for fostering co-innovation. The EIP-AGRI has a unique and valuable place in this co-innovation landscape but cannot engage equally effectively with all groups of AKIS actors for all purposes and should not be expected to do so. For some actors and some purposes, alternative routes to co-innovation may be more appropriate. Based on these assertions, we make three general recommendations that are addressed primarily to the EC, as well as national and (where appropriate) sub-national policy-makers and policy implementers.

Increase user participation in co-innovation and capitalise on any competitive advantage of particular types of intervention to appeal to harder-to-reach groups.

2014–2020 has been the first EU programming period where, through the EIP-AGRI, there has been an obligation to adopt the multi-actor approach. Some consortia deemed to be adequate in earlier EU Framework Programme projects would no longer be so in view of the emphasis in H2020 on farmer-advisor-researcher cooperation and knowledge sharing. The Interreg programme also has a specific requirement in terms of the involvement of multiple types of actors. This is not so for other funding instruments, such as LIFE(+), ERASMUS+ and for the reviewed non-project activities. Our findings suggest that the absence of such a stipulation has not necessarily led to users being excluded from such partnerships. On the contrary, users seem willing to take a prominent role in other types of reviewed partnerships, such as projects supported by other European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF) and non-project activities (Figure 6). Even so, other programmes can learn from DG AGRI’s strategy of co-designing the EIP-AGRI with the SCAR SWG on AKIS, which includes users’ representatives as well as policy-makers and academics, to enhance user participation.

Nonetheless, a simple requirement to include users in partnerships is unlikely to overcome the barriers to their effective participation. Inclusion in a multi-actor partnership does not necessarily guarantee involvement in the co-innovation process (Neef and Neubert 2011). Our data show that a broad range of actors beyond researchers, advisors and farmers/foresters take part in activities that are judged to involve high levels of co-innovation, but we did not explore possible hierarchies in these partnerships. This is an important topic for further research in order to understand how effective participation could be better incentivised or supported.

Administrative demands associated with the ‘projectification’ of innovation support can lead to the consistent exclusion of some groups (Andersson 2009; Arora-Jonsson 2017). Even in the EIP-AGRI, there is a continuing dominance of academic partners in our reviewed (especially H2020) projects (Table 3 and Figure 6). User participation in project consortia is to be encouraged, but this is not the only option for participation

in co-innovation. Many H2020 projects have the financial resources to set up ‘practice-led innovation networks’, ‘farmer innovation groups’ or similar structures to foster co-innovation between the ‘consortium’ and the ‘larger periphery’ ‘all along the project’. For relevant topics both in the forthcoming Horizon Europe and other EU and non-EU programmes, similar arrangements could be specified as a prerequisite for funding and included as a criterion in the proposal evaluation process.

Informal co-innovation networks that adopt a ‘localised approach’ and are more ‘bureaucratically light’ than project consortia are attractive alternative options for some groups of actors. They may give users more ‘space’ to co-innovate ‘on their own terms’. More research is needed on the extent to which these ‘alternative’ approaches foster co-innovation and on lessons that can be learned concerning novel forms of policy intervention. For example, following evaluation of a ‘concept note’, co-innovation partnerships could perhaps be awarded a small ‘pump-priming’ grant with no financial or other reporting obligations, apart from the need to prepare one or two EIP-AGRI ‘Practice Abstracts’ or equivalent outputs at the end of the co-innovation process.

Earlier, we emphasised the relevance of the embeddedness of users in social networks. In the 2021–2027 EU programming period, farm advisory services will promote user involvement in the AKIS and participation in OGs.³ Such an obligation could apply to some of the alternative opportunities for fostering co-innovation, and may require targeted training for advisors on the portfolio of available options at European, national, regional and/or local levels. Other facilitators, such as innovation brokers and ‘champion farmers’, should also be encouraged to consider options for co-innovation beyond the EIP-AGRI. Some harder-to-reach groups that do not use advisory services could perhaps be mobilised through community-level knowledge brokering hubs as proposed by Fieldsend et al. (2019), although it must be accepted that many users are simply not interested in co-innovation.

Creating synergies between policies and programmes remains challenging but provides potential for improved and differentiated involvement of users.

Our data have shown that users and/or their representative organisations are participating in co-innovation partnerships funded by many different programmes, as well as in non-project activities including those without external funding (Table 3). Also, the same multi-actor partnerships may be active in different types of projects (e.g. OGs and Interreg). These findings illustrate the value of synergies between policies and programmes in fostering user participation.

Enabling synergies between its programmes has long been an aspiration of the EU (EC 2014). The EIP-AGRI itself links policies and instruments concerned with co-innovation. There is a risk that more coordination may lead to even more bureaucracy, but there is potential for more sharing of good practice between programmes. For example, researchers and educational institutes mostly occupy a leading role in EIP-AGRI projects, while non-EIP-AGRI projects render a more diverse picture concerning actor participation. EIP-AGRI can learn lessons on widening user participation from these other programmes, suggesting that following through on the ambition of the EIP-AGRI to build bridges with other programmes is of great importance. By contrast, other programmes might consult with users and their representative organisations on how to make them, literally, more user friendly.

Consistency in terminology should be improved, and other programmes might usefully adopt terms used with success in the EIP-AGRI such as ‘AKIS’ and ‘multi-actor’.

However, the clumsy use of specialist terminology will discourage potentially interested partners and thus create division between those which are capable of being involved in such projects and those which are not. LIAISON research has indicated that ‘interactive innovation’ is an example of a term that is not well understood by AKIS actors. More research is required on the intelligent use of terminology in programming documents.

Synergies can be improved concerning support for the development of co-innovation partnerships. A helpful step would be to explore the potential for common actions between existing expert ‘contact points’, such as the EU’s ‘National Contact Points’ for the H2020, Interreg and LIFE programmes, on the cross-cutting theme of co-innovation. The CAP networks that will be set up by the Member States under their forthcoming CAP Strategic Plans will be required to service the information needs of a diversity of AKIS actors, not just academic organisations.⁴ Their expert support should extend beyond the EIP-AGRI to the wider range of programmes that can support co-innovation. We do not advocate the creation of yet more project databases to complement those that already exist. Such databases take a lot of resources to maintain and frequently contain errors and omissions, a shortcoming that even applies to the EIP-AGRI project database.

Earlier, we expressed concern about the relatively slow roll-out of the EIP-AGRI in the post-socialist EU Member States and noted that this issue might not be solved rapidly. The consequence is that there is a gap in EU support for co-innovation in some regions of the EU. Until such time that the EIP-AGRI is fully functioning, there is a particular need to highlight to users the opportunities for co-innovation provided by other funding programmes.

More attention should be paid to the role of value chain co-innovation in the AKIS.

With reference to the classification of Lamprinopolou et al. (2014), the involvement of some *direct demand/enterprise* (categories B and M) in our reviewed projects is relatively low (Table 3). This important activity of co-innovation along the value chain in the AKIS (EU SCAR 2012) is probably under-represented in our sample. Similarly, the involvement of *indirect demand actors* (categories G and N) is also low in some types of reviewed projects, notably OGs. This result may in part be a consequence of the continuing strong emphasis in policy discourse (and in the content of databases) on the research/researcher-led co-innovation paradigm. It might also reflect a distinction between the implicit EIP-AGRI focus on innovation as some kind of broad ‘public good’ and the ‘private good’ approach of food chain actors.

Many farmers and foresters prefer to co-innovate with those with whom they have developed trustful relationships through day-to-day contact such as input suppliers, food processors, retailers and indeed consumers, in activities that they see may result in fairly rapid financial returns. But many of these partnerships are, therefore, ‘under the radar’ of both policy-makers and academia. Analysis of them can yield further valuable insights into the nature of co-innovation, while some coordination at the policy level might further enhance the impacts of this type of multi-actor partnership.

Conclusion

The EIP-AGRI is clearly an important driver of co-innovation in the AKIS, but not the only one. It will receive a welcome increase in funding in the 2021–2027 EU programming period but only a few farms will ever directly participate in EIP-AGRI activities

(Fotheringham et al. 2016) and certain groups of farms are likely to be disconnected from these and other formal programmes. This is in part owing to the potentially weak implementation of the EIP-AGRI in the post-socialist EU Member States. While there is considerable overlap between the programmes reviewed in our study concerning the types of challenges addressed, solutions proposed and types of innovations supported, there is also a differentiation between them, and indeed there is a high added value in ensuring different starting points (e.g. from an environment perspective, or educational perspective). It is, therefore, necessary to accept the EIP-AGRI as just one part of a complex matrix of multi-actor co-innovation activities across Europe and the interlinking of agriculture, forestry and agri-food chain-related co-innovation programmes as a worthy aspiration. This should include the more effective targeting of programmes at groups of actors, especially users, that are currently not sufficiently engaged with them.

Notes

1. We prefer the term ‘user’ to ‘end user’ as it better reflects the farmers’ and foresters’ role in the innovation process.
2. In contrast to Knotter et al. (2019), we disaggregated our data for ‘individual farmers and foresters’ (F) from those of ‘representative/supporting organisations’ (O) such as Chambers of Agriculture. In Table 3, an additional column (F/S) has been inserted to show the percentage of each type of project containing at least one representative from the two groups.
3. Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing rules on support for strategic plans to be drawn up by Member States under the Common agricultural policy (CAP Strategic Plans) and financed by the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) and by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and repealing Regulation (EU) No. 1305/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Regulation (EU) No. 1307/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council. {SEC(2018)305final} -{SWD(2018)301final}, p. 101.
4. Article 113 of {SEC(2018)305final} -{SWD(2018)301final}, p. 109.

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